

Rifting-related mafic-ultramafic magmatism and ore potential in NE Fennoscandia

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Multiple stages of Paleoproterozoic rifting have been recorded in several cratons, which resulted in the break-up of the Kenorland supercontinent and later to disruption of individual cratons. These extensional tectonic events were associated with wide-spread mafic-ultramafic magmatism producing important ore deposits of Cr, Ti, V, Ni, Cu and PGE. We studied the geochemistry of Paleoproterozoic mafic-ultramafic volcanic rocks from different belts in NE Fennoscandia (Fig. 1) to constrain the fertility and sulfide saturation history of the magmas and their potential to form magmatic sulfide deposits.

Figure 1. Sampled volcanic formations shown by red squares on a simplified geological map of northern Finland (based on DigiKP, the digital map database of the Geological Survey of Finland, Version 1.0; available at: www.geo.fi/en/bedrock.html). 1 = Kiiminki Fm, 2 = Haukipudas Fm, 3 = Runkaus Fm, 4 = Jouttiaapa Fm, 5 = Vintaselkä and Matinvaaara Fms, 6 = Kuntijärvi Fm, 7 = Petäjävaaara Fm, 8 = Ruukinvaara Fm, 9 = Mäntyvaara Fm, 10 = Möykkelmä Fm, 11 = Sattasvaara Fm, 12 = Kautoselkä Fm, 13 = Vesmajärvi Fm. Abbreviations for geological units: CLGB = Central Lapland greenstone belt, CLGC = Central Lapland Granitoid Complex, KaB = Kainuu belt, KiB = Kiiminki belt, KuB = Kuusamo belt, LGB = Lapland granulite belt, PeB = Peräpohja belt, SaB = Salla belt, ÖiGB. The Pechenga belt is located outside the map in the Kola Peninsula, NW Russia.

The 2.5–2.45 Ga magmatism formed large layered intrusions in the Kola and Karelian cratons which are thought to be products of a large mantle plume event. The lowermost volcanic rocks in the Kainuu, Central Lapland, and Salla and Kuusamo belts belong to this event. They show relatively primitive magma compositions with high MgO contents and clear signatures of crustal contamination, comparable to the co-eval mafic dyke swarms. This group of volcanic rocks display moderate PGE contents with Pt ranging from 5 to 10 ppb. Primitive rocks show mantle-like Ni/Pt ratios, whereas more evolved rocks show clearly elevated Ni/Pt ratios indicative of sulfide saturation. The volcanic rocks in different belts show rather similar geochemical signatures, suggesting similar histories of magmatic evolution. The Runkaus basalt formation was probably derived from a similar magma that produced the 2.31 Ga mafic dykes in Russian Karelia (Stepanova et al. 2015). This group of basalts has relatively low PGE contents and low MgO contents, indicating that the magma has equilibrated with sulfide, probably in the source mantle due to low degree of partial melting in upwelling asthenosphere. Hence, this pulse of magma may have less ore potential to form economic PGE deposits.

The Jatulian stage volcanic rocks can be related to mafic dyke swarms across the Karelian craton. Volcanic rocks from different belts show variable geochemical features with either depletion or enrichment in LREE and were probably derived from diverse mantle sources. The basalts from the Peräpohja belt were evidently derived from a depleted mantle source, which has experienced different degrees of previous melting extraction. New PGE data show that the magma was rich in Pt and Pd, broadly similar to fertile basaltic rocks globally. These rocks show mantle like Ni/Pt ratios without signs of PGE depletion, indicating no sulfide saturation prior to final emplacement. Based on a similar approach, the post-Jatulian stage magmatism (e.g., Central Lapland, Kiiminki and Pechenga) is assessed to show a high ore-formation potential for magmatic sulfide deposits.

Different stages of magmatism across different belts generally show similar features. With the exception of the Runkaus formation, most magma pulses show broadly fertile PGE contents. The key factors controlling ore-formation may include the capability to form large magma chambers or dynamic feeder conduits and the access of external sulfur to form sulfide deposits.

References

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